

Gender Socialization among Secondary School Students: A Quantitative Study

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Abstract: Gender socialization is an essential developmental process for young people to become gendered individuals, learning roles, behaviors and expectations that are deemed appropriate for their gender. Although perceptions of gender equality seem to be changing, traditional gender roles influence the attitude and behavior of students, especially in a more conservative socio-cultural environment. This research was designed to explore gender socialization trends of high school students and to compare gender and locale differences. A descriptive quantitative survey design was utilized. The sample comprised 100 secondary school pupils, 50 boys and 50 girls, randomly selected from rural and urban schools. Data was obtained through the standardized Gender Socialization Scale which assesses parental, school, peer and media pressures. The analyses included descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and independent t-test. The findings indicated a substantial gender socialization, with peer and media as the most prevailing. Significant differences emerged between boys and girls and between rural and urban students and all dimensions were positively correlated, suggesting that gender socialization is a cumulative and multi-source process

Keywords: Cumulative process, Gender differences, Locale differences, Media influence, Peer influence

Introduction

Gender socialization can be conceptualized as the lifelong process wherein people acquire the culturally defined roles, behaviors and expectations of men and women (Bandura, 1977; Bussey & Bandura, 1999). Adolescence is especially salient period during which young people experience swift cognitive, emotional and social development and develop their personal identities within the context of family, school, peers and media (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). These agents of society work together to shape ideas of what it means to be masculine, feminine and how one should behave. Studies demonstrate that gender norms are not shaped from a singular perspective but are shaped through systems of interaction (Paul Halpern et al., 2016; Ward & Grower, 2020). Parents model and reinforce gender-typed behaviors, schools potentially reinforce stereotypes through curriculum and expectations, peers' pressure for conformity and media representations normalize traditional roles (Leaper & Friedman, 2007; Ward & Grower, 2020). These factors also have a major influence on their choice of academic subject, self-concept, career aspirations and relationships with peers (Galambos et al., 1990). Although there is

greater recognition of gender equality, traditional expectations continue to exist, most strongly within collectivist and patriarchal cultures (Desai & Andrist, 2010; Jejeebhoy & Sathar, 2001). Rural and culturally conservative settings typically impose more rigid role prescriptions for gender and sexuality, whereas urban communities provide greater access to egalitarian attitudes. Moreover, girls tend to a greater extent to internalize gender norms than boys, as a result of unequal gendered expectations and socialization (Paul Halpern et al., 2016; Leaper & Friedman, 2007). In light of the saliency of adolescence for identity development, it is crucial to examine how socialization agents collectively influence gender attitudes empirically. This study investigates gender socialization trajectories across parents, school, peers and media dimensions; and gender and locale variances in influence patterns. The findings contribute knowledge to gender-sensitive teaching and learning policies and practice.

Objectives of the study

- i) To find out the extent of gender socialization among the students of secondary school.
- ii) To investigate gender-wise variation in gender socialization.
- iii) To assess the difference between rural and urban students in gender socialization.
- iv) To study the impact of parental, school, peer and media.
- v) To find out the correlation among the facets of gender socialization.

Hypothesis

- **H₀₁**. There is no significant difference between boys and girls in gender socialization.
- **H₀₂**. There is no significant difference between rural and urban students in gender socialization.
- **H₀₃**. There is no significant relationship among the dimensions of gender socialization.

Material and Method

Research Design: This was a quantitative descriptive survey design.

Population: The population was all the secondary school students in classes IX and X.

Sample: The study involved 100 students of secondary school, which includes 50 boys and 50 girls with the equal number of 50 rural and 50 urban students. Participants were selected by simple random sampling.

Variables

a. Independent variables: Gender (boys/girls), Locale (rural/urban)

b. Dependent variable: Gender Socialization score

Tool: The gender socialization scale (GSS) is a validated tool that measures four areas of gender socialization: parental, school, peer and media influence.

Data Collection: Schools were informed and consent taken. The students completed the scale in a standardized manner.

Statistical Techniques: Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data, including mean and standard deviation for central tendency and variability, t-tests to compare the two groups and Pearson's correlations were calculated for parental, school, peer and media subscales of gender socialization to investigate the relationships between these factors.

Result and Discussion:

Descriptive Statistics of Gender Socialization Dimensions

The mean and standard deviation were computed for each gender socialization dimension (i.e., parental, school, peer, media influence) to represent the general trend and dispersion of the data among participants.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Gender Socialization Dimensions (Where N = 100)

Dimension	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Parental Socialization	34.82	5.21	High
School Socialization	32.45	4.87	Moderate
Peer Socialization	36.10	5.60	High
Media Socialization	38.55	6.02	Very High
Overall Gender Socialization	141.92	14.73	High

Source: Data compiled from primary survey conducted by the researcher (2025).

Findings: The degree of gender role socialization among the students of secondary school was found high. Prominent influences of Media and Peers revealed the significant effect, indicating that adolescents are still very much exposed to gender rules within their sources of information, being those digital platforms and peers.

Analysis: Peer groups have always been important for adolescent development and research overwhelmingly demonstrates gendered peer relations in adolescence. Teens are very prone to peer pressure because they want to fit in and peers play a looming role in influencing gender-related attitudes and behaviours (Kornienko et al., 2016). Empirically, peer socialization has been associated with adolescent change in gender identity and pressure for gender conformity (Kornienko et al., 2016), illustrating how normative peer contexts sustain gendered behaviours and attitudes.

Also, media exposure itself is a potent agent of gender socialization, which sustains traditional gender roles and gender stereotypes. Gendered expectations are often portrayed in media content and internalized by adolescents and research has suggested that media depictions play a role in forming and enforcing gender role stereotypes (Ward & Grower, 2020). (Annual Reviews) Systematic reviews also show that interpersonal factors, such as peer relationships, consistently influence young adolescents' development of gender norms and while the media's role is complex, it is an established factor in influencing societal gender-related attitudes and behaviours (Kågesten et al., 2016).

Taken together, these findings support the current finding that there are strong peer and media influences on gender socialization for secondary school children and that these social norms are internalised by young people, as they come to understand gender through everyday interactions and mediated representations of gender.

Gender-wise Comparison

Two-sample t tests were used to test for sex differences in parental, school, peer and media gender socialization for boys and girls.

Table 2: Mean Difference between Boys and Girls (t-test; Where N=100)

Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Boys (n=50)	138.24	13.95	2.41	0.018*
Girls (n=50)	145.60	14.82		

*Significant at 0.05 level

Source: Data compiled from primary survey conducted by the researcher (2025).

Findings: Girls scored higher than boys, which may be further evidence of greater internalisation of gender norms and could be due to more cultural and family pressure.

Analysis: Girls are more likely than boys to internalize traditional gender norms, a finding that is consistently supported by previous research and attributed to differences in how parents and the larger culture socialize children. Peer and family environments often tend to more strictly enforce gender-role expectations for girls—traits such as being nurturing, compliant and relationally oriented are emphasized (e.g., Paul Halpern et al., 2016, Groeneveld, van Berkel, Hallers-Haalenberg, & Mesman, 2018) and such trends are predictive of greater internalization of gendered norms during early stages of life. There is also evidence that caregivers may unwittingly give gender-typed treatment to girls and boys which influences early ideas of what behaviours and roles are appropriate for each (Leaper & Friedman, 2007). Also, cultural constructions of femininity and social expectations for girls often include adherence to prosocial and relational parameters and this has been linked with higher scores on measures of gender socialization or conformity to gender norms (Galambos, Almeida, & Petersen, 1990). Such tendencies are not isolated to one context as research has demonstrated that girls in particular tend to be more strongly pressured to adhere to gender specific behaviours from family, friends and in schools, thus promoting an even deeper internalisation of these gendered norms. The above studies support the present study’s finding that girls tend to obtain higher scores on gender socialisation than boys and these results further confirm that girls’ gender role internalisation may be challenged by cultural and family related expectations which aligns with well established developmental research.

Rural–Urban Comparison

Independent t-tests were conducted to examine differences in gender socialization among rural and urban students within the parental, school, peer and media spheres.

Table 3: Gender Socialization Scores by Locale (Where N=100)

Locale	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Urban (n=50)	136.10	13.40	3.12	0.003**
Rural (n=50)	147.74	15.20		

**Significant at 0.01 level

Source: Data compiled from primary survey conducted by the researcher (2025).

Findings: Rural students are more gender socialized, indicative of influence of traditional social structure.

Analysis: Research consistently demonstrates that rural adolescents show more traditional gender role attitudes than those living in urban areas, which is attributed to more conservative social structures, patriarchal ideology and less access to egalitarian ideologies in rural spaces. What rural families do more of is reinforce traditional gender roles, including more pointing toward the traditional division of labor at work and in the home and more prescriptions for gendered behavior from early ages. Empirical research has shown that rural areas tend to maintain more collectivistic and traditional-based social systems, in which community expectations, parental authority and cultural beliefs holds more impact on rural adolescents' gender perceptions (Desai & Andrist, 2010). By contrast, urban areas usually offer more opportunities to be influenced by a greater variety of role models, by more progressive educational methods and by mass media that have versions that contradict the stereotyped sex roles (Jejeebhoy & Sathar, 2001).

These results are consistent with the current finding that rural students have considerably higher scores on gender socialization, as traditional value systems along with more communal living in rural areas continue to have a stronger impact on gender norms than urban areas.

Correlation among Dimensions

Pearson's correlation coefficients were computed to assess the associations between the parent, school, peer and media dimensions of gender socialization.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix (Where N=100)

Dimension	Parental	School	Peer	Media
Parental	1.00	0.52**	0.48**	0.45**
School	0.52**	1.00	0.50**	0.42**
Peer	0.48**	0.50**	1.00	0.58**
Media	0.45**	0.42**	0.58**	1.00

**Significant at 0.01 level

Source: Data compiled from primary survey conducted by the researcher (2025).

Findings: All the dimensions were positively related, indicating that gender socialization is a multi-source and reinforcing process.

Analysis: The study of gender development provides consistent evidence that gender socialization occurs with multiple, interconnected socialization agents, such as family, school, peers and media, that create a system of gender norm perpetuation. Based on social learning and ecological perspectives, adolescents learn gender roles not from a single source but from the multiplex and reciprocal influences among different levels of the social ecology (Bandura, 1977; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Empirical evidence supports that parental, media and peer influence are strongly connected and have a cumulative impact on shaping an adolescent's gender related beliefs and behavior. Ward and Grower (2020) highlight the gendered family norms that are often reinforced by media-gendered messages about gender. Likewise, Paul Halpern et al., 2016, Calkoen, Groeneveld, Beukeboom and Mesman (2018) demonstrated that (children's) gender attitudes were strongly related to parental gender socialization, which was even more supported through peers. These related factors combine to form an accumulative and self-reinforcing process, which may explain the present study's finding that all of the dimensions of gender socialization were positively correlated. The results therefore lend support to the notion that gender socialization is a systemic and multi-agent process rather than a mono-dimensional concept.

Discussion

The study found a strong gender socialization process in the secondary school students across the board, with the media and peer group as the strongest influencers. It is consistent with previous findings that adolescents are vulnerable to peer norms and media portrayals that have strong impacts on individual beliefs, behaviors and identity (Ward & Grower, 2020; Kornienko et al., 2016). Digital media leads to even greater access to gendered messages that perpetuate stereotypical roles. Girls obtained higher scores than boys, which may reflect greater internalization of gender norms for girls as result of more intense cultural and family pressures, in line with the results of Paul Halpern et al., 2016 and Galambos et al. (1990).) Prior research also revealed more pronounced gender differences for girls than boys. Studenten op het platteland hebben op dit vlak ook hoger gescoord dan studenten uit steden, wat wijst op de hardnekkigheid van traditionele en patriarchale opvattingen in het platteland (Desai & Andrist, 2010; Jejeebhoy & Sathar, 2001). The positive inter-correlations between parents, school, peers and media suggest that gender socialization is a multi-source, cumulative and reinforcing process, in line with both ecological and social learning (Bandura, 1977; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). These findings emphasize the need for comprehensive, gender-responsive family-, school- and media-based interventions to enhance equality and diminish stereotypic norms among youth.

Testing of Hypotheses

To test the hypothesized predictions, the suitable statistical procedures were utilized. T-test was conducted to test the difference on gender socialization between boys and girls, between rural and urban students; Pearson's product-moment correlation was applied to explore the association among the dimensions of gender socialization.

The first null hypothesis (H_{01}), which presumed that no difference exists between boys and girls in gender socialization, was tested by the independent samples t-test. The calculated t-value for this t-test was also found to be statistically significant ($t = 2.41, p < 0.05$) and, thus, null hypothesis H_{01} stood rejected. Such a finding reveals a positive gender difference in gender socialization.

The t-test was also used to test the second null hypothesis (H_{02}) that claimed there would be no significant difference between the means of the urban and rural students. The t-value ($t = 3.12, p < 0.01$) was statistically significant and H_{02} was rejected indicating a significant difference in terms of locale.

The third null hypothesis (H_{03}) which predicted that There is no significant correlation among the factors of gender socialization, was tested using Pearson's correlation. Results showed significant positive correlations between parental, school, peer and media factors ($r = 0.42 - 0.58, p < 0.01$). Hence, the results confirm that gender socialization is a multi-dimensional and reinforcing process and H_{03} was rejected.

Educational Implications:

The study findings call for immediate gender sensitive educational policies and practices that enhance equity and deconstruct stereotypical norms in the context of education. The curriculum developers need to weave gender equity and inclusion principles within all disciplines, while educators should be sensitized and trained regularly to recognize and mitigate gender biases in teaching and learning processes and materials. Given the strong impact of media and peers on adolescents, schools need to include media literacy and life-skills education that enables

students to think critically about gender representations and counter damaging stereotypes. Parental awareness programmes and school–community collaboration can also contribute to positive gender outlooks, while peer-led initiatives such as debates, clubs and mentoring can build mutual respect, empathy and inclusive conduct among young people.

Future-Directions:

The present study could be further strengthened if future researchers could generalize to larger and more heterogeneous sample from various regions and of different socio-economic status. Longitudinal research is needed to ascertain the progression of gender socialization across the life span and stages of development. Intervention research in this area, which assesses the impact of school-based gender sensitization programme, would also help in generating evidence based on practicality for policy and practice. Mixed-methods designs, in which surveys may be combined with interviews or observations, are also particularly well suited to exploring how adolescents lived experiences. In addition, cross-cultural and comparative research could reveal particularities and universals in gender socialization.

Conclusion

The study concludes that family, school, peers and media are the key agents of gender socialization among senior high school students. Media and peer groups were found to be the most influential sources, illustrating the new social context in which young people organise their gender identities. Locale and gender based differences are testimony to the ongoing influence of cultural/traditional systems of defining gender expectations, most notably for rural girls but also to some extent for urban girls and rural boys. The positive correlations among all levels indicate that gender socialization is a multiple-source and reinforcing process. Such educators who are unwilling to view these findings through the lens of challenge to traditional gender roles and serve their students in the best way possible with gender responsive pedagogy are significantly underserved by this study. Schools should be places of transformation and where young people are encouraged to critically examine gender roles and to be more inclusive in their thinking. Educators have a vital role in advancing a more just society and in doing so they have the opportunity to shape the society of the future by embedding gender consciousness in curricular and co-curricular programming. In the end, the study adds empirical weight to the debate on gender and education and highlights coordinated strategies for the family, school and media as pivotal for propelling balanced and progressive gender socialisation for the adolescent.

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